

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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ESCAPING A CODE STROKE: EVALUATION OF ESCAPE ROOM METHODOLOGY ON
ACCEPTANCE OF STROKE MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Given the clinical necessity to expedite diagnostic workup and treatment for patients suffering from a stroke, new evidence-based stroke management guidelines have recognized the importance of early activation of stroke teams and have emphasized streamlining workflows. These recommendations and best practices profoundly rely on nursing education and stroke team training. Escape rooms have been utilized in healthcare as an unconventional and alternative education methodology to promote critical thinking and team collaboration; however, few studies examined its impact on nursing acceptance of evidence-based guidelines specific to reducing time metrics and improving patient outcomes. This doctoral project examines the impact of a stroke escape room on nursing attitudes and acceptance towards the American Heart and American Stroke Association 2019 Stroke Management Guidelines. Using the Seven Stars of Knowledge framework, the escape room was implemented at a 552-bed community hospital during nursing orientation with 40 newly hired nurses with varying years of experience and nursing background. Desired outcomes focused on increased nursing knowledge and attitudes towards acceptance of current evidence-based stroke guidelines. The Evidence Based Practice Attitude Scale was used to measure these outcomes pre and post stroke escape room implementation. Participant scores resulted in an overall increase in attitudes towards acceptance of current stroke guidelines. The successful piloting of an escape room as an alternative method of teaching yields the potential for its integration into other avenues of nursing education. Exploration of years of experience and generational differences can further determine the effectiveness of escape rooms to produce more education-focused outcomes and therefore guide the implementation and study of escape rooms in clinical practice.

Keywords: stroke, escape room, nursing, attitudes, evidence-based guidelines, ischemic stroke, nursing education, neuroscience, educational game, gamification.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vi
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	3
Purpose Statement.....	4
Supporting Framework	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Overview.....	8
Clinical Stroke Significance and its Related Outcomes	9
Delays in Endovascular Treatment	10
Perceived Barriers to Acute Stroke Management.....	12
Game-Based Learning and Escape Rooms.....	13
Summary.....	15
METHODS	16
Design, Setting, Participants.....	16
Ethical Considerations and Institutional Review Board.....	17
Procedure	18
Demographic Questionnaire	21
Pre- and Post-Survey.....	21
Data Collection and Storage Procedure	23
Data Analysis and Evaluation Procedure.....	24
Resources, Proposed Budget, and Timeline	25
Summary.....	26
RESULTS	27
Descriptive Statistics: Participant Characteristics	27
Pre and Post Survey Analysis	27

DISCUSSION.....	29
Recommendations.....	30
Implications.....	31
Strengths and Limitations	32
Conclusions.....	33
REFERENCES	35
APPENDIX A: Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behavior.....	44
APPENDIX B: Figure 2: Theoretical Application of Theory of Planned Behavior.....	45
APPENDIX C: Figure 3: Model of Game-based Learning	46
APPENDIX D: Figure 4: Stevens Star Model of Knowledge	48
APPENDIX E: Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary	49
APPENDIX F: Escape Room Summary and Guide	51
APPENDIX G: Demographic Questionnaire.....	58
APPENDIX H: Adapted Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS ©)	59
APPENDIX I: EBPAS©, Factor Loadings, Cronbach’s Alphas, and Scoring.....	60
APPENDIX J: Projected DNP Project Budget	61
APPENDIX K: Table 1: Descriptive Statistics.....	62
APPENDIX L: Table 2: Mean EBPAS© Domain Scores.....	64
APPENDIX M: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages	65
Figure 5: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages All Domains.....	65
Figure 6: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 1 Requirements	66
Figure 7: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 2 Appeal	67
Figure 8: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 3 Openness	68
Figure 9: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 4 Divergence	69

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Background

With stroke remaining the leading cause for morbidity around the world, approximately 800,000 people will experience a stroke annually in the United States (Benjamin et al., 2017). Approximately eighty-seven percent of all strokes are ischemic, and 80% of these types of strokes are due to intracranial arterial occlusions (Benjamin et al., 2017; Saini et al., 2021). Advances in acute stroke management with thrombolysis and endovascular treatment continue to place emphasis on timely recognition and reduction of delay to care (Mulder et al., 2018). Despite increased availability of thrombolytic and intra-arterial therapies over the past decade, only a small portion of patients arrive within the treatment window (Saini et al., 2021). Early recanalization of large artery occlusions is vital in improving functional neurological recovery and overall clinical outcomes in patients suffering an acute ischemic stroke (AIS) (Cheung et al., 2018; Mulder et al., 2018). Stroke not only impacts one's neurological and functional status, but the overwhelming economic burden is estimated to be \$140,048 in healthcare costs per person (Rochmah et al., 2021, p. 2).

Clinical outcomes following an AIS highly depend on the patient's age, stroke severity, and occlusion location; therefore, protection of the ischemic penumbra and rapid re-establishment of cerebral blood flow is key in reducing expansion of the core infarct (Smith, 2019). Several studies have further stressed that these occluded cerebral vessels will continue to cause metabolic disturbances that can result in brain tissue necrosis, thus leading to permanent disability (Smith, 2019). Researchers have examined the impact of treatment delays to acute thrombolytic therapy and endovascular revascularization and have found an annual decline of 6% in patients who present to the emergency department within 24 hours of symptoms onset; therefore, time to acute stroke intervention remains the single most important quality metric for

all hospitals (Saini et al., 2021). With the expansion of the therapeutic time window of mechanical thrombectomy (MT) for treatment of AIS with large vessel occlusions (LVO) beyond 4.5 hours up to 24 hours, there has been a collective effort across systems of care to implement quality initiatives to target delays to MT (Powers et al., 2019).

Although recent American Heart Association and American Stroke Association Guidelines (AHA/ASA) have proposed door to device within 90 minutes of arrival, many hospitals continue to be challenged with improving quality of stroke care and reducing treatment delays (American Heart Association, 2018; Powers et al., 2019). Despite initiatives involving expanding community and emergency services education in addition to in-hospital workflow changes, MT interventions continue to be delayed (Powers et al., 2019). These time-dependent metrics reflect a complex clinical stroke management workflow involving delicate coordination of multiple departments and disciplines; therefore, evaluation of the impact of perceived barriers towards clinical practice guideline adherence should be further explored. There remains limited research examining the influence of these perceived barriers on delays to acute stroke treatment (Pines et al., 2020).

AHA/ASA Target: Stroke

In 2010, the AHA/ASA introduced Target: Stroke (AHA, 2010), Phase I, a nationwide quality initiative aimed at improving clinical outcomes and increasing survivability for AIS patients (Fonarow et al., 2011; Fonarow et al., 2014). Within the first year of its launch, 1,200 hospitals aligned together and committed to reducing door to intravenous thrombolytic therapy within 60 minutes or less of arrival, in 50% of eligible stroke patients (Powers et al., 2019). Based on a 2014 study that evaluated the effectiveness of Target: Stroke, Phase I, Fonarow et al. (2014) found a significant reduction in in-hospital mortality and long-term disability in patients

treated within 60 minutes. This success propelled the development of Target: Stroke Phase II in 2015 which challenged hospitals to increase the goal for 60-minute door to needle times from 50% to 75% of eligible stroke patients through the implementation of 12 best practice strategies (AHA/ASA, 2017).

As more advanced therapies to treat AIS patients with LVOs continued to evolve, updates to the AHA/ASA stroke guidelines for acute stroke management began to credit MT to improving revascularization and complete cerebral reperfusion, and therefore became a mainstay treatment for stroke in 2015 (Powers et al., 2019). The importance and value of MT was reflected in the 2018 Target: Stroke, Phase III update. The primary goal for arrival to first pass of thrombectomy device was set to be 90 minutes or less in at least 50% or more eligible AIS (AHA, 2018; Powers et al., 2019). These Target: Stroke goals not only have set the standard for improving stroke systems of care, but also have challenged hospital teams to incorporate best practices to streamline processes and ultimately eliminate delays.

Problem Statement

Despite implementing the recommended initiatives of Target: Stroke, Phases II and III, the time to intervention remains prolonged. Although awareness of early stroke recognition has expanded, there remains a lack of expedited stroke team and nurse response once the decision for thrombolytic therapy or MT has been made by the physician. Workflow changes can lead to resistance of adoption of guidelines; therefore, attitudes toward practice change should be further explored (Pines et al., 2020). Game-based learning, in which games are used to enhance learners' motivation and increase knowledge and skills, has been progressively used in nursing-based education (Gómez-Urquiza et al., 2019). An escape room is an evidence-based education method of game-based learning that has demonstrated improved clinical motivation and attitudes towards

practice change (Adams et al., 2018; Gómez-Urquiza et al., 2019; Molina-Torres et al., 2022).

Given the recommendation of national guidelines set by AHA/ASA, there is an imperative need to review the literature and implement an evidence-based education method to increase new hire nurses' attitudes towards expedited stroke treatment, thereby improving adoption and adherence to the recommended guidelines, and ultimately leading to better patient outcomes.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this doctoral project is to examine if implementation of an educational stroke escape room activity improves new hire nurses' attitudes by 15% towards evidence-based acute stroke management guidelines in over 3 months.

Project Objectives

The objectives of this doctoral project are to:

- Increase new hire nurses' knowledge base regarding current AHA/ASA 2019 Acute Ischemic Stroke Management Guidelines
- Increase overall attitudes towards adherence to current AHA/ASA 2019 Acute Ischemic Management Guidelines
- Pilot a new method of education for acute stroke management as it relates to rapid response and recognition of stroke
- Explore length of nursing experience (i.e., new graduate nurse versus experienced nurse) associated with adoption of AHA/ASA 2019 Acute Ischemic Stroke Management Guidelines

Supporting Theoretical Framework

Behavior and Attitudes

Attitudes have been presumed to be based on multiple components: emotional responses, behavioral intentions, and cognitions (Ostrom, 1969). Behavioral reactions to objects or events are thought to be guided by these internal perceptions and feelings; therefore, some researchers suggest that medical training and education should not only incorporate skill development, but also increase focus on development of attitudes (Ozkalay & Karaca, 2021). On the other hand, there remains a disparity between attitudes and the corresponding behavior. The formal traditional approach to education is challenged with engaging the students to target specific interpersonal interactions and attitudes to better predict behavior responses to situations (Archer et al., 2008). To better understand how attitudes impact behavior, the theory of planned behavior was utilized as the framework for this doctoral project.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

TPB is one of the most influential psychosocial behavior models that evaluates how decision making is affected by psychological variables such as internal beliefs (Ajzen, 1991). Although TPB was based on the theory of reasoned action, which originally proposed that intention drives behavior, TPB further examines this intention by evaluating the attitudes towards behavior and any perceived social or environmental norms (Ajzen, 1991). Figure 1 in Appendix A describes the three main belief factors that influence intention which then drives behavior.

Ajzen's TPB (1991) suggests that an individual will successfully engage in a behavior if there is intent that is guided by negative or positive beliefs about the behavior (attitudes). Additionally, this intent is also based on perceived social pressures (subjective norms) (Ajzen,

1991). Lastly, intent can derive from one's perceived ability to perform the behavior (perceived behavioral control) (Ajzen, 1991). Attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral controls influence intention which in turn prompts behavior; therefore, TPB provides an organized theory-based approach to integrating attitude evaluation to support practice change and adoption (Li et al., 2019).

In this doctoral project, to support acceptance and adherence to the AHA/ASA 2019 acute stroke management guidelines, TPB suggests initial assessment of the intent to adhere to the guidelines. This intent to engage in this behavior will be influenced by the negative or positive attitudes towards the guidelines. Therefore, to better assess this attitude, evaluation of present knowledge of the guidelines in addition to personal sentiment about how guidelines impact current practice is critical. Secondly, evaluation of the social pressures to follow these guidelines should also be explored. TPB suggests that the more favorable the attitude and acceptance of subjective norms, the more likely the person will perform the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). These social pressures to change behavior and accept the guidelines are important factors to consider in this doctoral project. This can be accomplished through a survey by questioning personal beliefs that are motivated by compliance with others' expectations.

Lastly, the construct of perceived behavioral control is based on self-efficacy and controllability of one's behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The ease to which the guidelines can be implemented would need to be addressed. According to TPB, if there is a positive attitude towards the guidelines, social acceptance, and perceived ability to carry out the guidelines, the intention is strong, and the behavior should occur (Ajzen, 1991). Utilizing this model, the stroke escape room will incorporate activities to promote positive attitudes toward the updated guidelines. Outcomes will address any discrepancies between social expectations and perceived

ability to integrate the guidelines into current practice. These newly acquired values will support a vested interest and therefore increase attitude-behavior correspondence (Ajzen, 1991). Figure 2 in Appendix B depicts the integration of TPB as the framework for this doctoral project.

Review of Literature

Literature Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search using CINAHL, EBSCO Host, PUBMED, Google, and MEDLINE was completed for this doctoral project. Search criteria consisted of the following terms: *endovascular treatment*, *stroke*, *escape room*, *game-based learning theory*, *nurses' attitudes*, *barriers to stroke*, and *delays in stroke*. Boolean terms “and” and “or” was used between the search terms. The search was further limited to English peer-reviewed journal articles dating between 2016-2021. The inclusion criteria considered were also based on the objective of implementing an escape room activity to improve nurses' attitudes towards expedited stroke treatment. The review yielded 2,396 articles that implemented various game learning activities, inclusive of an escape room. Based on this doctoral project's aim, 2,377 articles were excluded, and the review of literature therefore only included articles that supported the significance of expedited stroke intervention, stroke clinical outcomes, provider attitudes towards acute stroke management, and impact of escape room education. Articles that did not define associated stroke patient outcomes to acute stroke intervention were excluded as they did not apply to the aim of this doctoral project. Articles that were not available in English and did not have a defined study design were also excluded.

Strength of the articles was based on the Johns Hopkins Nursing evidence-based practice models and guidelines (Dang, 2022). This model suggests a high strength level of evidence as I to III, whereas low to moderate strength as levels IV and V (Dang, 2022). Preference was given to journal articles with levels of evidence I-III due to its scientific basis; however, articles with a lower level of evidence were also included if they were appropriate and stronger evidence levels

were unavailable. Criteria were based on relevance to the objective of the doctoral project and therefore, only 19 articles met the criteria for inclusion.

Clinical Stroke Significance and its Related Outcomes

The National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, a division of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, indicated that the median stroke prevalence rate was 3.0% in the United States and that by 2030, 3.4 million Americans will have had a stroke (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017). This represents a 20.5% increase in prevalence since 2012 (CDC, 2017). Based on the rising volume of strokes occurring annually, the AHA computes that every 40 seconds, someone in the United States has a stroke (Virani et al., 2020). This increased stroke incidence and prevalence further acknowledges stroke as a preventable disease and that rapid recognition of stroke symptoms is necessary for preventing systemic complications to prompt early treatment and optimize stroke outcomes (Jahan et al., 2019; Powers et al., 2019; Virani et al., 2020).

Despite advances in stroke management and a shift of focus to expedited treatment, the literature still indicates that stroke remains the leading cause of long-term disability (Benjamin et al., 2017; Saini et al., 2021; Virani et al., 2020). Data across multiple prospective studies demonstrate that even after initial recovery from a stroke, overall function, cognitive ability, and quality of life continue to decline (Benjamin et al., 2017; Dhamoon et al., 2017; Hendén et al., 2018). Additionally, the associated economic costs of acute and post-acute stroke care are enormous. The average cost per patient in the U.S. is \$59,900 which can amount up to \$103.5 billion of overall costs annually (Saini et al., 2021; Strilciuc et al., 2021; Virani et al., 2020). These overwhelming detrimental physiological and financial burdens of stroke not only warrant

process improvement changes for rapid care, but also encourages nurses to develop a sense of urgency when time is brain.

Delays in Endovascular Treatment

Although there are multiple trials that clearly identify the clinical benefit of early revascularization for stroke patients, there are inconsistencies in implementing standard best practice strategies to reduce door to device times for stroke endovascular therapy (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Reynolds et al., 2016; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Four studies aimed to evaluate these variances in practices and their related impact on neurological outcomes (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Reynolds et al., 2016; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Overall, there is strong evidence supporting practice change in managing acute ischemic strokes, given that delays in treatment can result in poor functional neurological status (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Reynolds et al., 2016; Vukasinovic et al., 2019).

Two of the studies reviewed are retrospective studies, as clinical time metrics were abstracted from medical records (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019). This design is a common weakness in the literature as the study results are heavily dependent on accurate and complete documentation. Patients who are lost to outpatient follow-up also impact the quality of data abstraction. All samples of the quantitative studies were convenient, and the authors adequately included detailed inclusion criteria (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). A strength of the quantitative studies is that the large sample sizes reduced the risk of a Type II error (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Discrepancies in the findings, however, can be attributed to the differences in vessel occlusion location and the severity of strokes included in the individual study samples. This variance in the samples' acuity limits the external validity of the results.

All four studies that reviewed delays to acute stroke treatment were level three evidence, and they supported the need for standardization for the treatment of stroke, given the varying level of provider expertise and hospital system resources (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Reynolds et al., 2016; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Patients that were included in the studies reviewed had high-severity strokes that required acute endovascular treatment for large vessel occlusions (Cheung et al., 2018; Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). These studies similarly suggest that achievement of door to revascularization time relies on a coordinated effort between multiple disciplines and departments (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Although all three quantitative studies did not indicate a consistent acceptable door to reperfusion time goal, establishment of revascularization is patient dependent in relation to their vascular anatomy, and therefore, treatment fidelity intra-procedure is difficult to obtain (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). There was a noted treatment bias in one study as conscious sedation was purposely utilized in less severe strokes, and therefore door to reperfusion time may have been impacted (Vukasinovic et al., 2019). The qualitative study provided evidence to support the concept that adherence to stroke guidelines requires continuous education efforts and direct feedback on the rationale behind standardized stroke management (Reynolds et al., 2016). Based on the evidence, stroke management is clearly patient dependent, and there are multiple confounding variables that can ultimately delay treatment, such as varying provider knowledge base and limited hospital system resources (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Each study uniquely focused on different aspects regarding the chain of management of acute ischemic stroke patients requiring endovascular treatment. Although there is a longer delay to treatment in off-hours, and providers may biasedly select general anesthesia over conscious sedation, the studies' varying

results imply that there is a clear gap in adherence to standardized best practices (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019). Further investigation of these barriers to acceptance is warranted. All three quantitative studies found no statistically significant difference in the quality of revascularization based on the timing of reperfusion (Hendén et al., 2018; Jahan et al., 2019; Vukasinovic et al., 2019).; however, one study found improved statistically significant functional outcomes in patients with shorter door to treatment times (Cheung et al., 2018). Across studies, there is a variance in identifying which aspect of the stroke workflow has the greatest impact on the delay to treatment; therefore, there is an imperative need to evaluate barriers to expedited stroke care to improve the efficiency of care in time-sensitive stroke interventions.

Perceived Barriers to Acute Stroke Management

With the extended treatment window up to 24 hours from symptom onset for eligible acute ischemic stroke patients, AHA/ASA guidelines have been developed to support its use for improved patient outcomes (Powers et al., 2019). Despite the evidence demonstrating the impact of delayed treatment, integrating and applying these clinical guidelines into practice remain slow (Baatiema, de-Graft Aikins, et al., 2017; Baatiema, Otim, et al., 2017). Although the barriers to adherence have not been fully understood, research has provided some insight as to reasons for such impediments to clinical guideline adoption. For example, several studies highlight the lack of available organizational resources and support due to limited funding and staffing (Baatiema, Otim, et al., 2017; Hill et al., 2020). Other articles indicate provider unawareness of the new evidence-based therapies for stroke in addition to deficient knowledge base in their application (Reynolds et al., 2016). Most of the studies have a significant overlap of barriers and recurrent themes of low adherence secondary to the structural and organizational component to stroke

care. Administrative support and adequate resources are vital in successful adoption (Baatiema, de-Graft Aikins, et al., 2017; Baatiema, Otim, et al., 2017; Lowther et al., 2021). However, some studies identified health professionals' unwillingness as a major contributor to the underutilization of the clinical practice guidelines (Lowther et al., 2021; Moore et al., 2018). There is a clear demand to further examine barriers and focus on the clinical behavioral components to enhance acceptance of evidence-based acute stroke care recommendations. To further explore the intrinsic motivating factors as it pertains to removing practice barriers, gamification was found to facilitate dependent individual and contextual factors to promote acceptance (Moore et al., 2018).

Game-Based Learning and Escape Rooms

An escape room was originally started in Japan as a game where a team of players would collaborate to complete puzzles, tasks, and solve clues to accomplish a specific objective under a set timer (Zhang et al., 2018). There is strong evidence that supports the utilization of game-based strategies in education; however, it was only recently that escape rooms have been utilized in medical settings (Gates & Youngberg-Campos, 2020). As millennials and generation "z"-ers continue to enter the nursing workforce at a rapid rate, professional development, and education have been tasked with implementing new and innovative methods of engaging learners (Gates & Youngberg-Campos, 2020). Nursing education has been encouraged to expand its teaching strategies to take a multi-modal approach to address the learning needs of multiple generations (Gates & Youngberg-Campos, 2020; Moore et al., 2018). Escape rooms have been used as effective teaching methods for increasing health care learner satisfaction and motivation as they are actively engaged in meaningful learning (Adams et al., 2018; Gómez-Urquiza et al., 2019).

Numerous studies indicate the escape rooms provide a safe and interactive environment to increase knowledge among students (Gómez-Urquiza et al., 2019; Molina-Torres et al., 2022; Veldkamp et al., 2020). The complex problem-solving aspect of escape rooms maximizes the development of social and cognitive skills as the learners navigate through multi-faceted puzzles (Schei et al., 2020). Evidence shows that although these puzzles may be challenging, learners are motivated to perform and contribute to team development as they engage in the escape room exercises (Schei et al., 2020). Across studies, escape rooms have been increasingly utilized in health care settings to advance clinical knowledge and competence and promote nursing professionalism (Adams et al., 2018; Molina-Torres et al., 2022). The design of educational games is critical in achieving learning outcomes (Plass et al., 2015). The cognitive, emotional, motivational, and sociocultural aspects of effective game design create a foundation to maximize the learner's development (Plass et al., 2015). Figure 3 in Appendix C depicts three key elements that serve as the basis of the game-based learning model: challenge, response, and feedback.

Escape rooms grounded in game-based learning (GBL) have been associated with improved learner motivation, engagement, and social interaction (Guckian et al., 2020). An escape room activity integrates critical thinking and teamwork into active learning through a hands-on experience of puzzles and problem-solving games (Adams et al., 2018). Therefore, escape rooms must incorporate unique challenges that would elicit an interactive response to develop learner empathetic simulation (Veldkamp et al., 2020). The structure of these puzzles further contextualizes the necessary knowledge and skills to ensure active learning and educational engagement (Veldkamp et al., 2020). The response of each challenge, according to GBL, in turn must provide a method to which a learner can offer feedback as this contributes to the learner's autonomy and accountability (Subhash & Cudney, 2018). This escape room activity

should include direct input from the learner to ensure knowledge transfer. GBL also encourages the use of awards and penalties as motivational constructs as part of the feedback system to effectively engage learners (Plass et al., 2015). Therefore, the design of the escape room will incorporate positive and negative feedback prompts into each challenge, thus leading to solutions and accomplishment of learner outcomes. Escape rooms provide a unique experience for learners to foster motivation and education.

Summary

Given the current evidence to support the clinical significance of delays in stroke care, there remains a clear gap in understanding caregiver perceptions and attitudes that prohibit acceptance and implementation of evidence-based stroke guidelines. The positive outcomes of increased learner motivation and engagement lend to the use of escape rooms as a means of providing innovative activities to improve awareness and utilization of these guidelines. As a result of this literature review, this doctoral project will examine the impact of this novel educational strategy on the learners' perceptions and attitudes toward stroke care.

Methods

The purpose of this doctoral project was to implement an educational activity based on escape room methodology to improve attitudes toward acceptance of stroke management clinical guidelines. To further strengthen the theoretical framework of this project, the Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation © was utilized to guide the design and implementation of this project. To better organize approaches to research evidence integration into practice, this Star Model is comprised of five major stages of knowledge transformation: 1) discovery research, 2) evidence summary, 3) translation to guidelines, 4) practice integration, and 5) process, outcome evaluation (Stevens, 2004; Stevens, 2015). Refer to Appendix D for the figure of the Star Model of Knowledge Transformation ©.

Project Design

The project leader developed, planned, and implemented an educational activity in the form of an escape room based on the recently published AHA/ASA stroke management guidelines aimed at new hire registered nurses. The main objective of this doctoral project is to increase the overall attitudes towards successful adoption of these guidelines. Evaluation components included the use of a valid and reliable tool to assess participant attitudes towards adoption of evidence-based practice specific to stroke. To determine the effectiveness of the escape room educational activity, a program evaluation design with a pre-survey and post-test survey was utilized. Participants' willingness to adopt these guidelines was assessed following the escape room activity.

Project Site and Population

After obtaining facility permissions, the DNP project took place at a 552-bed community Southern California hospital that is Joint Commission Certified Comprehensive Stroke Center.

The escape room activity was implemented during the bi-weekly nursing orientation.

Participation in this project is voluntary. Verbal agreement for participation in the pre-test and post-survey aspects of the project's evaluation was obtained. Refer to Appendix E: Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary. Participants consisted of all new-hire registered nurses from various nursing departments that are new to the organization.

Instruments

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from the organization and the university was obtained prior to implementation of the project. Appendix E contains a project summary that was reviewed prior to implementation of the escape room activity. Participation in completing the questionnaire and evaluations of the project was voluntary. Participants reserved the right to withdraw before submitting surveys or not participate at any time without penalty. Additionally, participants had the right to refuse to answer any question(s) for any reason. Surveys were anonymous, and no identifiable information will be included in the questionnaires. The pre and post surveys were created in Qualtrics for abstraction. Access to the surveys and results was only permissible through username and protected password authentication. Access was only granted to the project lead and committee chair.

Although the nurses had the option to opt out of participating in the pre and post surveys, they were unable to opt out of participation in the stroke escape room as that is standard practice for nursing orientation specific to stroke. Given the anonymity of the surveys, the only time the participant could not withdraw was after the surveys had been submitted. There was no feasible way to identify the participants' information or data at that time. This doctoral project posed minimal risks to the participants.

Procedure

As previously discussed, the five points of the Star Model of Knowledge Transformation© was used for this doctoral project.

Star Point 1: Discovery Research

This star point is the knowledge gathering phase; therefore, the project lead performed an extensive literature review based on traditional scientific inquiry to provide evidence to support the implementation of an escape room as it relates to acute stroke management.

Star Point 2: Evidence Summary

Based on this literature review, this stage occurs simultaneously with *Star Point 1*. The project lead compiled a thorough synthesis of the evidence. Research and clinical evidence were reviewed and revealed the success of implementing an escape room to improve learner attitudes and confidence in the context of increasing knowledge specific to clinical practice.

Star Point 3: Translation into Practice Recommendations

The third stage utilizes the evidence from the literature to provide formal practice recommendations for integration into practice. The following were the steps for this project:

1. Development of a project participant agreement and summary to remain in alignment with the ethical considerations of this project. Refer to Appendix E for the project summary.
2. Design of the stroke escape room. The project lead developed an educational stroke escape room activity to disseminate the AHA/ASA acute stroke management clinical guidelines to new hire nurses. Refer to Appendix F: Stroke Escape Room Summary and Guide.

Escape Room Educational Methodology Procedure. A pre-briefing session included a discussion with the participants about the data collection. Refer to Appendix F: Stroke Escape Room Summary and Guide, for specific details of the stroke escape room activity. Once the pre-surveys were completed, the project leader divided the participants into groups of 3-5 to allow greater individual participation in the activity. Groups alternated completing the escape room. The project leader played the patient scenario video, a cinema-like overview of the patient's situation and the overall objective of the activity. Afterward, the escape room instructions and rules were read to the participants.

Following the reading of these regulations, the project lead provided the participants with a written patient scenario that provided a history of present illness and a description of the patient. The participants were instructed on the initial location of the first clue. The first clue required the participants to first assess the patient. Puzzle pieces were hidden throughout the room. Once the participants located the puzzle pieces, they assembled the pieces to find a hidden message. The message revealed that the patient had developed an acute focal neurological change, prompting the participants to activate a code stroke. The code to the locked box next to the telephone in the patient room is 711. Once they entered this code, the next clue prompted the participants to obtain equipment from the medication room.

The medication room had a locked box that required a key. A key was hidden among the items located in the room. The participants worked together to find the key in the item that related to the vital diagnostic information that must be obtained during a code stroke. When the key was located, it opened the locked box that revealed the next clue. The next clue suggests that the participants should localize the patient's symptoms. Among the items in the medication room was a blue-light flashlight. This helped them find the hidden code written in invisible ink that

was located under the correct area of the brain in the picture. Once the code was correctly identified the code, a locked box opened and led them to the computer. This clue encouraged the participants to order a diagnostic scan.

At the computer area, the participants found index cards with various order items: non-contrast computed tomography (CT) Brain, CT angiogram Head, CT angiogram Neck, CT Perfusion, magnetic resonance (MR) (MR imaging Brain, MR angiogram Head, MR angiogram Neck. On the back of these cards will be numerical codes. The correct scan was a non-contrast CT Brain with the code '911'. This code unlocked the next clue that prompted the participants to reassess the patient. Once they returned to the patient's room, there were several stroke scales among the patient. The scoring was written in invisible ink and the participants used the flashlight to identify the correct score for the patient based on the clinical presentation. The secret message required them to return to the computer room for their final clue. There was a laminated card that contained the BEFAST acronym (Balance, Eyes, Face, Arms, Speech, Time). Next to this message is a cryptex. The BEFAST letters will open the cryptex that contains the message "Congratulations, YOU SURVIVED A CODE STROKE!"

Overall, this exercise required the participants to actively review the evidence-based protocol for acute management of a stroke patient requiring possible intervention. The project lead conducted a debriefing session to discuss overall participant sentiment about the escape room in addition to accomplishment of its objectives. The EBPAS© post-survey was administered directly after the debriefing sessions. Both briefing sessions occurred in the same area as the escape room.

3. Obtaining supplies for the stroke escape room.
4. Developing a demographic questionnaire.

Demographic Questionnaire. The demographic questionnaire (see Appendix G: Demographic Questionnaire) included the following: professional and departmental information (job function and specialty area, if applicable), years of clinical experience, education level, certification status, length of previous experience in caring for or management of stroke patients, and current knowledge of the 2019 AHA/ASA stroke management guidelines. There was no identifiable information documented on the demographic questionnaire.

5. Identify an evidence-based survey and instrument to measure the nurses' attitudes toward acceptance of clinical guidelines.

Attitude Assessment (Pre-survey and Post-survey). To align with the objectives of this doctoral project, the Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS©) was used with permission from Gregory A. Aarons, Ph.D. Permission to utilize and adapt the EBPAS© validated tool was obtained from the original author Dr. Gregory Aarons on March 16, 2022, through an email correspondence. The purpose of this self-report quantitative instrument is to measure participants' attitudes towards adoption of evidence-based practice (Aarons, 2004; Aarons et al., 2010). The EBPAS© is comprised of four sub-scales: Appeal, Requirements, Openness, and Divergence as it relates to participants' willingness to accept new practices (Aarons et al., 2010). The Appeal subscale evaluates the intuitive perception of evidence-based practice (Aarons, 2004; Aarons et al., 2010). The Requirements subscale examines providers' acceptance to implement the new practice if it was required (Aarons, 2004; Aarons et al., 2010). The Openness subscale measures one's inclination to adopt the new practice. Lastly, the Divergence subscale addresses the perception of deviating from evidence-based practice to current practice (Aarons, 2004; Aarons et al., 2010). The Aarons (2004) and Aarons et al. (2010) studies concluded that the EBPAS showed moderate to good internal consistency and reliability,

respectively, for the total score (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.77$ and 0.79) and subscales scores excluding Divergence (α range = $0.78-0.93$), with lower reliability estimates for Divergence (α range = $0.59-0.66$).

This tool includes 15 questions based on a 0 to 4 Likert scale: 0 = not at all and 4 = to a very great extent (Aarons, 2004). Refer to Appendix H: Adapted EBPAS©, for the adapted version of the EBPAS©. Possible attitude scores could range from 0 (disagreed completely) to 60 (agree greatly) (Aarons, 2004). The scoring of the scales was completed by computing a mean score for each set of items in each subscale. If some items are not completed, computing the means may be allowed for only one fewer item that are comprised of the subscale (Aarons, 2004). The total score of all subscales combined was obtained pre and post the escape room activity. Prior to computing the total score, the items from the subscale (Divergence) must be reversed score and the subscale must be recomputed (Aarons, 2004). Once this score is obtained, the total score can be computed to yield the total EBPAS© (Aarons, 2004). Refer to Appendix I: EBPAS© Items, Factor Loadings, Chronbach's Alphas, and Scoring, for the calculation score guidelines for the EBPAS© tool. This same questionnaire was administered prior to and at the conclusion of the escape room to assess and compare their scores before and after the educational activity. All data from the demographic questionnaire and pre and post surveys were reported in aggregate format.

Star Point 4: Practice Integration

During this stage, the project lead began the process of implementing the stroke escape room activity.

1. Presented project proposal to the Nursing Research Council at the project hospital site and obtained formal project approval

2. Obtained IRB review from the project's hospital site and from California State University, Los Angeles
3. Provided the project summary to the general education manager who oversees the nursing orientation
4. Implemented project for a period of 3 months or until at least 30 participants were obtained
 - a. Allowed approximately 10 minutes to complete the EBPAS© pre-survey and demographic questionnaire.
 - b. Completed the EPBAS© pre-survey.
 - c. Conducted the stroke escape room activity.
 - d. Once the escape room activity and the debriefing session were completed, the EPBAS© post-survey was administered by the project lead. During the briefing and debriefing sessions, the participants were allowed to ask questions.
 - e. Concluded implementation.

Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation

During this last stage, under the guidance of the project committee chair, the project lead collated the data and evaluated the outcomes of this project.

Data Collection and Storage. The EBPAS© was adapted to assess participant attitudes towards adoption of the AHA/ASA stroke management guidelines. The pre-/post-survey format was selected to measure the overall impact of the escape room intervention. The de-identified aggregated data of the pre and post survey results was collected into a secure web application called Qualtrics© for building and managing databases.

Data collection occurred over the span of 1 month and consisted of 40 participants. Data collected in Qualtrics© remained in this secure web-based application that is user-password protected.

Data Analysis and Evaluation. The project leader reviewed and prepared the data in collaboration with the project committee chair. The mean scores of the subscales of the EBPAS© tool and the total scores were calculated. The data analysis of this project was measured primarily through the application of frequencies, descriptive statistics, and t-test evaluations of individual item responses and grouped domain responses to evaluate statistical significance. Frequencies of the individual item responses were evaluated through univariate analysis to describe the project participants. Paired t-tests were used to compare mean differences between the EBPAS© score pre and post intervention. The tool guidelines for calculating the total EBPAS© score from the subscale and total scores were used to ensure accuracy of data interpretation.

Since no associated participant data was obtained during the data collection process, the project leader worked with the committee chair to prevent data entry errors. Collation of the total scores pre and post escape room was used to assess the achievement of this project's objectives of overall improvement in provider attitudes towards adopting evidence-based practice. EBPAS© pre and post subscale and total scores were displayed initially in a table format for comparison. Group means differences in the individual scores were also assessed. To further investigate demographic trends, exploratory data analysis was completed through data visualizations (i.e., bar charts) and summary tables.

Resources, Proposed Budget, and Time

The initial development of the escape room required a substantial amount of time dedicated to planning and outlining the flow of the activity. The facility provided the project lead with the space to conduct the escape room and the task-training devices. The project lead developed all puzzles and games and purchased the items such as the locks, blue-light flashlight, invisible ink, and the cryptex for a nominal cost. The project lead created the pre-debriefing video that explained the case scenario for the escape room. A video release was obtained. The majority of the items in the medication room were donated expired items from the project lead's unit. The project committee chair collaborated with the project lead to ensure proper statistical analysis was conducted.

A cost analysis of this project was performed. Items that will be examined include staff salaries, time to complete the escape room, time for education and briefing sessions, any incidental materials used, and the cost of materials and supplies. Refer to Appendix J: Projected DNP Project Budget, for the proposed budget. The total cost for this project averaged \$1,620.15 when considering the average cost of a nurse's hourly salary.

The timeline of this proposed DNP project started in September after official Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained from both the organization and the university. A formal presentation of the doctoral project took place at the facility at the end of April during the hospital research council. Additionally, the university proposal defense included a detailed overview of the project purpose, literature review, framework, and methods. Based on the feedback of the nursing research council and university faculty, a committee chair letter of approval was required prior to moving forward with the IRB application at both the university and the facility. This facility approval letter was submitted to the project committee chair.

Given that this project involved the use of survey procedures of public behavior and there were no identifiers linked to the subjects, the project lead applied for IRB exemption. Once IRB approval was obtained from the university and facility, the project lead implemented the data collection aspect of this project for one month to obtain at least 30 participants. After data was compiled, the project lead contacted the research council at the facility to disseminate lessons learned and project findings.

Summary of Implementation Plan

The on-site facility DNP student mentor in conjunction with the chair and committee members of this doctoral project, was presented with the evidence obtained from the literature review. The resources, timeline of project, and IRB approval process for implementation of the escape room activity and data collection was discussed formally and presented at the university and at the facility. Development of the escape room was based on the AHA/ASA evidence-based guidelines for stroke and was presented to the key stakeholders (facility administration, project committee members, DNP cohort colleagues, and faculty). Formal IRB exemption for project implementation was obtained. The escape room activity was implemented during the new hire nursing orientation over one month with 40 participants. Pre- and post- surveys were collected through a secure web-based application. Pre-briefing and post-briefing sessions were conducted to enhance the learner's experience. The project lead primarily conducted data analysis in collaboration with the committee chair. Finally, data was prepared for interpretation and the results and associated practice implications were formally presented at the university and facility.

Results

Descriptive Statistics: Participant Characteristics

A total of 40 full time newly hired registered nurses participated in this doctoral project. All 40 participants completed the pre- and post-survey. The majority were bachelor's prepared new-graduate female nurses, ranging in age between 22 and 30, with less than two years of nursing experience. More than 40% of the participants were hired into the emergency room department. Additionally, at least 50% had experience with the AHA/ASA 2019 Stroke Guidelines. The descriptive statistics of the project's participants are outlined in Table 1 of Appendix K.

Pre and Post EBPAS© Survey Analysis

R programming language software was used to analyze the data that was collected by Qualtrics. Paired *t*-tests were utilized to compare mean EBPAS scores pre- and post-implementation of the stroke escape room. Preliminary and post-intervention surveys were paired anonymously through the Qualtrics application. Using a one-sample *t*-test, the post-intervention scores were compared to the means of the pre-survey. Across all four main domains (Requirements, Appeal, Openness, and Divergence), there is a significant medium difference between before ($M = 2.6$, $SD = 0.7$) and after ($M = 3.1$, $SD = 0.4$), $t(14) = 2.8$, $p = .014$, implementation of the stroke escape room. Higher scores indicate more positive acceptance and attitudes towards adopting evidence-based practice, whereas lower scores represent less positive beliefs, except for the divergence scale, in which the score is reversed. This 15-item Likert scale EBPAS© survey has established reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.59$ to 0.90) with validity supported by correlation with relevant variables (Aarons, 2004).

The EBPAS© scale was designed to evaluate a clinician's attitude towards adopting evidence-based guidelines into practice (Aarons, 2004). In reviewing the bar graphs of the results, improvements were noted in the participants' individual responses to 14 of the 15 statements of the EBPAS© scale. Table 2 in Appendix L contains the summary of pre- and post-survey means of all 15 items of the EBPAS©. The results are grouped by the main domains of the EBPAS© scale in Figures 6-9 in Appendix M. Appendix M contain bar graph representation of the EBPAS© mean average scores pre and post escape room. The reliability of all survey metrics was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Survey items demonstrated acceptable reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.854$).

Discussion

The primary purpose of this doctoral project was to examine the impact of a stroke escape room on newly hired nurses' attitudes toward adopting evidence-based practice guidelines. There was a statistically significant medium difference in overall mean scores pre- and post-implementation of the stroke escape room. The results provided insight into the value and effectiveness of a non-traditional educational methodology in a healthcare setting for nursing. Although a majority of the literature reported the positive effects of escape rooms on students' teamwork, confidence, collaboration, and critical thinking skills (Adams et al., 2018; Gates & Youngberg-Campos, 2020; Molina-Torres et al., 2022), this project successfully applied Ajzen's theory of planned behavior and utilized the EBPAS© tool to demonstrate the impact of the escape room towards a positive attitude towards the AHA/ASA stroke guidelines that would ultimately influence their behavior or use of the guidelines in practice.

One of the objectives of this project was to increase new hire nurses' knowledge base regarding current AHA/ASA 2019 Acute Ischemic Stroke Management guidelines. 21 of the 40 participants prior to implementation of the escape room indicated previous experience with the current guidelines. The curriculum of the escape room provided the participants with full experience in applying these guidelines to practice. Each puzzle was methodically developed to facilitate the participant's ability to understand the acute stroke management workflow to expedite treatment and diagnostic work-up of the stroke patient.

The third objective of this project was to pilot a new method of education for acute stroke management as it relates to rapid response and recognition of stroke. Before implementing this new teaching strategy, the previous nursing orientation for stroke at this facility utilized the traditional lecture approach to reviewing the current guidelines. The project lead successfully

integrated the escape room into the new hire nurses' orientation. Although anecdotal feedback was not part of the outcomes of this project, the lead reviewed the participants' evaluations of the stroke escape room. Participants found the activity to be engaging, while others reported that the escape room promoted teamwork and the overall intent and importance of expediting imaging to determine patient eligibility for treatment. Some participants also indicated that innovativeness of the escape room increased their competency in acute stroke management.

Lastly, the objective to explore generational differences and years of nursing experience associated with adopting guidelines was not achieved. A regression analysis to evaluate this relationship was not completed due to the data collection method and limited time allotment for the escape room activity during nursing orientation. The evaluation of this relationship would require a more complex model, such as a generalized linear mixed model, as the data would need to provide binary answers (new graduate nurse or not). Furthermore, one would have to consider repeating the measurements on the participants for a limited time.

Recommendations

This project provides the foundation for future use of escape rooms in other avenues of nursing education: nursing orientation, unit-based onboarding processes, skills days, etc. The project's findings suggest that the escape room is an effective and innovative method of education to impart critical skills to expose learners to evidence-based practice. Students can experience making mistakes in a clinical-based simulation to apply personal experience and learned skills into practice.

Although this study did not explore the relationship between new graduate and experienced nurses with the adoption of the current guidelines, the project provided an alternative perspective on the potential effectiveness of an escape room as a new educational

approach. Given the current landscape of educating digital native learners, educators are tasked to provide fast-paced information and implement more interactive methods of education. This study can be utilized as a framework for other applications and purposes of an escape room. Other projects can focus on training inter-professional teams or further development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The diverse nursing background and experiences of this project's participants enabled the project lead to provide critical opportunities to employ professionalism, communication, and clinical reasoning through the escape room.

Another recommendation is to further explore the influence of participant characteristics on EBPAS. From the data results, the project captured various demographics: gender, years of experience, specialty, and educational background. Future projects can examine the relationships between potential influences on the EBPAS© scores.

Implications

Ajzen (1991) proposed that the more favorable the three constructs of his theory, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavior control, the stronger the person's intention to engage in the behavior in question; therefore, the four domains of the EBPAS© tool paralleled this theory: intuitive appeal of evidence-based practice, probability of adoption given the requirements to do so, openness to new practices based on evidence, and perceived deviation from evidence-based interventions in current practice.

Addressing the construct of subjective norms and attitudes of Ajzen's theory, the post-intervention increase in scores specific to the domains of requirement, appeal, and openness supports the potential effectiveness of an escape room of providing exposure to new practice guidelines. These three domains can strengthen the influence of changing or improving one's behavior towards fully adopting evidence-based practices. Based on the findings, normative

expectations and motivations appear to significantly influence the nurse's intention to implement the stroke guidelines. The appeal and one's openness had the most significant change in mean differences and therefore suggested that the escape room can greatly impact nurses' perception of utilizing research in practice.

However, three of the four questions within the divergence domain increased. These items address the attitudes and perceived behavior control aspects of Ajzen's theory. The project findings suggest that the participants favored clinical experience over evidence-based practice, indicating that overall, the participants felt that clinical decision making is heavily based on experience instead of research. Management of the stroke patient is complex; therefore, evidence-based practice guidelines help direct care, not to replace moral judgment derived from clinical experience. Most participants had less than two years of nursing experience and would need greater exposure to more evidence-based practices to ensure quality, expedited stroke care.

Strengths/Limitations

One strength of this DNP project was using a valid, reliable tool to examine the nurses' attitudes toward evidence-based practice adoption. The EBPAS© tool aligned with this project's theoretical framework of Ajzen's theory of planned behavior. It allowed for more consistent and accurate data results for analysis and interpretation. Another strength of this DNP project was the design of the project. All participants were encouraged to participate in the stroke escape room as part of the standard nursing orientation, which increased the survey response rate. A final strength of the DNP project was the low associated budget to create the escape room, thus making implementation financially feasible and affordable.

One limitation of this project was the time constraints of implementing the escape room. The project lead only had approximately 30-45 minutes to complete the data collection, debrief,

and set up the room. Also, given the increased demand for nurses, there was an influx of newly graduated nurses; therefore, most participants had less than two years of nursing experience. This can be modified but applying the stroke escape room in other avenues of nursing education as skills days or training sessions. Another limitation of this project is that the escape room was not developed by an interprofessional team. Even though the project focused on exploring newly hired nurses' attitudes, Ajzen's theory regarding subjective norms indicates the societal importance of interprofessional feedback to influence the clinical decision-making process. Consistency in the delivery of the escape room is also a limitation. Given that the project lead had to prompt or provide clues to the participants, there were variances in how the puzzles were solved between participant groups. A final limitation of the project was the small sample size and small community hospital. Although this was a quality improvement project, a larger group of participants with various backgrounds in a different hospital setting, such as a county hospital, may yield different results.

Conclusions

In summary, this DNP project provided evidence that an escape room, when used in a nursing orientation setting, can positively influence newly hired nurses' attitudes towards adopting evidence-based practice guidelines for stroke. The results of this project are consistent with the current literature and information on healthcare escape rooms with regard to increasing learner confidence, communication, and team collaboration. These concepts set the foundation for caregivers and providers to deliver high quality care with the aim of utilizing resources more efficiently and improving patient care outcomes. This project can contribute to the creation of future applications of the escape room to other aspects of patient care management. The integration of this safe, effective, low-cost, evidence-based intervention into healthcare education

had demonstrated potential to impact clinical practice governed in influencing one's personal intention for change. This project serves as another bridge between practice and research and further opened the dialogue for more innovative educational practices.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behavior

Figure 1

Theory of Planned Behavior

Note. This figure is a pictorial representation of the well validated model of the relationship between attitudes and behavior. From “The Theory of Planned Behavior,” by I. Ajzen, 1991, *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2) p. 182

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-t](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-t)

Appendix B

Figure 2: Theoretical Application of Theory of Planned Behavior

Figure 2

Theoretical Application of Theory of Planned Behavior

Note. This figure is an adapted pictorial representation of the well validated model of the relationship between attitudes and behavior as it applies to this doctoral project. Adapted from “The Theory of Planned Behavior,” by I. Ajzen, 1991, *Journal of Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2) p. 182 ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-t](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-t))

Appendix C

Figure 3: Model of Game-based Learning

Figure 3

Model of Game-based Learning

Note. This figure illustrates the three main components of game-based learning: challenge, response, and feedback. From “Foundations of Game-based Learning,” J. L. Plass, B. D., Homer, & C. K. Kinzer, *Educational Psychologist*, 50(4), p. 262

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2015.1122533>

Appendix D

Figure 4: Stevens Star Model of Knowledge

Figure 4

Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

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Note. This figure provides an outline of steps used to guide the implementation of this doctoral project. From “ACE star model of knowledge transformation” by Stevens, K.R., Academic Center for Evidence-Based Practice. University of Texas Health Science Center San Antonio. <https://www.uthscsa.edu/academics/nursing/star-model>

Appendix E

Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary

Project Title: Escaping a Code Stroke: Impact of Escape Room Methodology on Nurses' Attitudes Towards Acute Stroke Management

Doctoral of Nursing Practice (DNP) Student: Diana D. Tai, MSN AGACNP-BC, ACNS-BC, CCRN, SCRNP, CNRN

Providence (DNP) Mentor: Teresa Wavra, DNP RN

Faculty Team Leader: Ayman Tailakh, Ph.D., RN, Faculty Committee Member

Faculty Committee Member: Cinthya Vasquez Sotelo, DNP, FNP-C, ENP-C, Faculty Team Leader

Project Description: An escape room uses a series of puzzles and clues to solve problem and work as a group to escape the room. The purpose of this project is to assess knowledge and perceptions of participants before and after the escape room experience. Participants will have 5 minutes to answer a demographic questionnaire that includes the following: professional and departmental information (job function and specialty area, if applicable), years of clinical experience, education level, certification status, length of previous experience in caring for or management of stroke patients, current knowledge of the 2019 AHA/ASA stroke management guidelines. Participants will also be asked to complete a 15 question Likert-Scale survey before and after the escape room experience. You will not be locked in the room; you will be able to exit the room at any time. The escape room is part of the research project. There are 5 puzzles that are based on the 2019 AHA/ASA stroke management guidelines. There will be individual puzzles at each station that will lead you to the next clue. After reading the initial scenario, you will work together as a group to solve each puzzle until time of 30 minutes has been reached or completion of all 5 puzzles. This entire activity will take approximately 45 minutes. 15 minutes will be dedicated to survey completion and 30 minutes will be allocated for the escape room. Time is dependent on completion of the surveys and escape room.

Confidentiality: All information will be recorded anonymously and reported as aggregate data. Surveys will be collected by anonymous submission. Project lead will leave the room during survey submission. The data will then be stored in a locked filing cabinet in a locked office. Data will be entered into a password protect database once all surveys have been collected. Paper surveys will be destroyed after 7 years from the completion of this project.

Risks and Benefits: The benefits to participation in the escape room include knowledge enhancement and increased self-perception in diagnostic functions and management of risk in acutely ill patients. Your participation will contribute to the body of knowledge surrounding use of escape rooms as an educational tool. There are minimal risks associated with your voluntary participation in the escape room and participation pre and post escape room surveys. You have the opportunity to skip any questions that you do not wish to answer.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in the pre and post survey is voluntary. Participation in the escape room is also voluntary.

Right to Withdraw: You obtain the right to withdraw from this activity at any time. You will not be penalized for withdrawal.

Questions: Contact information for Principal Investigator: Ayman Tailakh, Ph.D. RN, Email: Ayman.Tailakh@calstatela.edu

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix F

Escape Room Summary and Guide

Overview of the Escape Room

Picture this:

A group of six to eight people wants to experience this Escape Room. They gather outside the room and receive rules and a scenario to get them started. The beginning scenario gives them a clue to find nine puzzle pieces hidden throughout the room. The group has 30 minutes to solve all the puzzles and escape the room. The team is provided three free clues during the experience. Additional clues cost one minute and are added to the final time.

Rules

Please keep the following information in mind:

1. You have 30 minutes to escape.
2. If you need to exit at any time, feel free to. However, the clock will not stop.
3. When you unlock an item, please place the lock in the designated bucket.
4. There will be a moderator present. This moderator will not talk. They will only communicate with you by writing.
5. You can ask your moderator for three free clues. Every clue you ask for after the three will cost one additional minute added to the final time.
6. Please do not force open items. If you try to force things, you will break them.
7. Remember to be efficient but accurate.
8. Ask yourself, "How fast can I complete the room by following all the appropriate steps?" Do not skip over steps to break out faster.
9. Everything you need, you will find in the room.
10. No cell phones!
11. Good luck and have fun!

Intro Scenario

Ms. DT is a 45 year old Hispanic female with a past medical history significant for HTN, high cholesterol, and diabetes who presents to the emergency room for dizziness and headache. She was admitted to PCSU for observation. Initial CT was negative for any intracranial abnormality. This patient has been a real PUZZLE for the staff to treat as her symptoms appear vague. Good luck in PIECING together information in this room. Remember... you have to start with the basics.

FLOW OF THE ROOM

The first clue is that the nurses need to ASSESS the patient first. They will need to go to the center of the room and find the puzzle pieces underneath the patient.

Once the puzzle pieces are found and the puzzle is assembled, the group will see:

CODE 711 will be used to open the portable safe located at the phone. Inside the safe will be a notecard with this message:

Great! You have activated a code stroke by calling 711.

While you are waiting for RRT to arrive,

what would information do you need to have?

This clue will take them to the medication room. Inside the room will be a few items

- Glucometer
- Blood pressure
- Pupillometer
- IV fluid
- Lab tubes
- Labetalol
- Black light
- Gloves
- Tape
- Alcohol swabs
- Washable marker

In the blood pressure cuff, will be a hidden key. The key will open a tacklebox and they will find cards to label Circle of Willis with the following clue:

You need to localize your symptoms...which artery is affected?

The participants will go to the Circle of Willis poster and label the arteries.

Nursing Orientation: Brain lobes; participants will scan brain to obtain code.

On the back of the correct artery, will be code LDL to open the box next to the COW poster. Inside the box will be the following clue:

Congratulations! You have localized your symptoms.
How will you confirm your suspicion? What test
will you order?

This will lead them to a computer and find the next clue with multiple orders.

- CT Brain
- CTA Head
- CTA Neck
- CT Perfusion
- MRI Brain
- MRA Head
- MRA Neck

The CT brain will have CODE 911 on the back of the card that will open the box with the following clue:

You're back from CT scan. What is your next assessment?

This will take the participants back to the patient and there will be several NIHS laid out. They will be blank, and they will have to use the black light from the med room to obtain the right NIH. The secret message will say: you will need to document several stroke measures. The stroke measures will be in an envelope labeled EPIC.

Balance
Eyes
Face
Arms
Speech
Time

They will use the red letters to open the cryptex.

In the cryptex: It will say

Congratulations, YOU SURVIVED A CODE STROKE!

Supplies

Item/Purpose	Quantity	Where to Purchase
9 Piece puzzle	1	 simple-puzzle-piece-patterns.pdf
lock box (711 code)	1	Amazon
Phone	1	Hospital Supply
Medication room supplies (see above list)	1	Hospital Supply
Boxes with latches for locks	2	Amazon
Cryptex	1	Amazon
Combination locks	3	Staples

Appendix G

Demographic Questionnaire

Acute Stroke Management Demographic Questionnaire

THANK YOU for your assistance in participating in the following demographic questionnaire, and pre and post Stroke Escape Room survey for the purposes of my doctoral quality improvement project. The questionnaire and responses to the survey are ANONYMOUS and WILL NOT be linked to your name/role.

1. **What is your job title? Please check or write in response.**
 - Staff Nurse
 - Charge Nurse
 - Manager
 - Director
 - Educator
 - Advanced Practice Nurse (Midwife, Nurse Anesthetist, Nurse Practitioner, Clinical Nurse Specialist)
 - Other: _____
2. **What is your specialty? Please check or write in response. You may check more than one answer.**
 - Emergency medicine
 - Procedural (Interventional Radiology, Cardiac Cath Lab)
 - Neurology
 - Trauma
 - Maternal Child
 - Cardiac Telemetry
 - Critical Care
 - Surgery/Operating Room
 - Other: _____
3. **What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? If currently enrolled, check highest degree received.**
 - High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent (for example: General Educational Development (GED))
 - Some college credit, no degree
 - Trade/technical/vocational training
 - Associate degree
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Doctorate degree
4. **Are you:**
 - Full-time
 - Part-time
 - Per diem
5. **How many years of nursing experience do you have?**
 - <2 years
 - 2-5 years
 - 6-10 years
 - 10 + years
6. **Do you currently hold a specialty board certification? (i.e. Stroke Certified Registered Nurse (SCRN), Critical Care Registered Nurse (CCRN))**
 - Yes: Please specify _____
 - No
7. **Do you have any experience in caring for stroke patients (hemorrhagic and ischemic)?**
 - Yes, how many years? _____
 - No
8. **Do you have any experience with 2019 American Heart/American Stroke Management Guidelines?**
 - Yes
 - No

Appendix H

Adapted Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale

Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale

EBPAS© Gregory A. Aarons, Ph.D.

Reference: Aarons, G. A. (2004). Mental health provider attitudes toward adoption of evidence-based practice: The Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale. *Mental Health Services Research*, 6(2), 61-74.

The following questions ask about your feelings about using the **2019 American Heart/American Stroke Management Guidelines**.

Manualized therapy refers to any intervention that has specific guidelines and/or components that are outlined in a manual and/or that are to be followed in a structured/predetermined way.

Fill in the circle indicating the extent to which you agree with each item using the following scale:

0	1	2	3	4
Not at All	To a Slight Extent	To a Moderate Extent	To a Great Extent	To a Very Great Extent

	0	1	2	3	4
1. I like to use new types of therapy/interventions to help my clients.....	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I am willing to try new types of therapy/interventions even if I have to follow a treatment manual.....	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I know better than academic researchers how to care for my clients.....	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I am willing to use new and different types of therapy/interventions developed by researchers.....	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Research based treatments/interventions are not clinically useful.....	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Clinical experience is more important than using manualized therapy/treatment.....	<input type="radio"/>				
7. I would not use manualized therapy/interventions.....	<input type="radio"/>				
8. I would try a new therapy/intervention even if it were very different from what I am used to doing.....	<input type="radio"/>				
For questions 9-15: If you received training in a therapy or intervention that was new to you, how likely would you be to adopt it if:					
9. it was intuitively appealing?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
10. it "made sense" to you?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
11. it was required by your supervisor?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
12. it was required by your agency?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
13. it was required by your state?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
14. it was being used by colleagues who were happy with it?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
15. you felt you had enough training to use it correctly?.....	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix I

EBPAS© Items, Factor Loadings, Cronbach's Alphas, and Scoring

Reference:

Aarons, G. A. (2004). Mental health provider attitudes toward adoption of evidence-based practice: The Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale. *Mental Health Services Research, 6*(2).

Item #	Scale	Factor Loading	Alpha
	Scale 1: Requirements		.90
12	Agency required	.99	
11	Supervisor required	.88	
13	State required	.78	
	Scale 2: Appeal		.80
10	Makes sense	.89	
9	Intuitively appealing	.83	
14	Colleagues happy with therapy	.56	
15	Enough training	.55	
	Scale 3: Openness		.78
2	Will follow a treatment manual	.61	
4	Will try therapy/interventions developed by researchers	.81	
1	Like to use new therapy/interventions	.62	
8	Would try therapy/interventions different than usual	.66	
	Scale 4: Divergence		.59
5	Research based treatments/interventions not useful	.65	
7	Would not use manualized therapy/interventions	.76	
6	Clinical experience more important	.42	
3	Know better than researchers how to care for clients	.34	
	EBPAS Total		.77

SCORING THE SCALES

The score for each subscale is created by computing a mean score for each set of items that load on a given subscale. For example, items 11, 12, and 13 constitute Scale 1. If there is missing data in your data set, computing means may be done allowing for one fewer items than make up the scale.

COMPUTING THE TOTAL SCORE

Only for the total score (not the individual scale scores), items from subscale 4 (Divergence) **must be reverse scored** and the subscale score recomputed. After the reverse scoring is complete, then a mean of the scale scores may be computed to yield the mean score for the total EBPAS.

You may contact Dr. Aarons by email at: gaarons@ucsd.edu

Appendix J

Projected DNP Project Budget

Escape Room Items

Item	Quantity	Cost	Total
Hand sanitizer	NA Available in room	0.00	0.00
Index Cards	1 pkg	1.00	1.00
Laminating of escape room items	1 pkg of laminating sheets	9.15	9.15
Clorox wipes	4	5.00	20.00
Black light flashlight	1	10.00	10.00
Pens	1 pkg	5.00	5.00
Locks	5	5.00	25.00
Cryptex	1	45.00	45.00
Poster	1 pkg	5.00	5.00
Total			120.15

Projected Costs

Item	Quantity	Cost	Total
Total Equipment costs	NA	120.15	120.15
RN Time (hourly wage ~\$50.00)	1 hour	50.00 (30 nurses total)	1,500.00
Project Leader time	80 hours	0.00	0.00
Total			1,620.15

Appendix K

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Measure	Frequency/Count	Percentage
Gender		
Male	8	20%
Female	32	80%
Age		
18-21	0	0%
22-30	21	53%
31-40	15	38%
41-50	0	0%
50+	4	10%
Employment Status		
Full-Time	40	100%
Part-Time	0	0%
Per Diem	0	0%
Level of Education		
Doctorate	0	0%
Master's Degree	0	0%
Bachelor's Degree	39	97.5%
Associate degree	1	2.50%
Other	0	0%
Job Title		
Staff Nurse	37	93%
Manager	1	3.3%
Educator	1	3.3%
Other	1	3.3%
Specialty		
Emergency Medicine	16	41%
Procedural (Interventional Radiology/Cath Lab)	0	0%
Neurology	2	5%
Maternal/Child	0	3%
Critical Care	1	5%
Trauma	2	0%
Cardiac Telemetry	8	21%
Surgery	6	15%
Other	4	10%
Stroke Experience		
Yes	27	68%

Measure	Frequency/Count	Percentage
No	13	32%
Experience with 2019 AHA/ASA Stroke Guidelines		
Yes	21	52.5%
No	19	47.5%
Certification Status		
Stroke Certified Registered Nurse	5	38%
Certified Neuroscience Registered Nurse	0	0%
Critical Care Registered Nurse	4	31%
Other (CEN, stroke scale certified)	4	31%
Years of Experience		
15+ years	2	5%
10-15 years	1	2.5%
6-10 years	6	15%
2-5 years	8	20%
<2 years	23	57.5%

Note. Table depicts percentage of project participants for each descriptive measure.

Appendix L

Table 2: Mean EBPAS© Domain Scores

Table 2

Mean EBPAS© Domain Scores

Domain	Pre-survey Mean	Post-survey Mean	Difference
Scale 1: Requirements	8.13	8.92	0.79
Scale 2: Appeal	12.25	13.82	1.57
Scale 3: Openness	11.11	12.71	1.6
Scale 4: Divergence (Reverse Scored)	6.81	10.63	3.82
Total	38.3	46.08	7.78

Note Table 2 contains pre and post intervention means for each domain. Divergence domain is reversed scored.

Appendix M

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages

Figure 5

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages All Domains

Note. Figure contains pre (blue) and post escape (red) room intervention EBAS mean averages for all domains.

Figure 6

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 1 Requirements

Note. Figure contains pre (blue) and post escape (red) room intervention EBAS mean averages for Scale 1, Requirements.

Figure 7

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 2 Appeal

Note. Figure contains pre (blue) and post escape (red) room intervention EBAS mean averages for Scale 2, Appeal

Figure 8

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 3 Openness

Note. Figure contains pre (blue) and post escape (red) room intervention EBAS mean averages for Scale 3, Openness

Figure 9

EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Scale 4 Divergence

Note. Figure contains pre (blue) and post escape (red) room intervention EBAS mean averages for Scale 4, Divergence